

Slotted-Hidden-Gap (SHG) connection for square hollow section bracing members under cyclic loading

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ABSTRACT

The Slotted-Hidden-Gap (SHG) connection is an improved version of the conventional welded tube-to-gusset connection between square hollow section (SHS) braces and framing elements used in Concentrically Braced Frames (CBFs). It offers an enhanced performance without the need for additional steel plate reinforcement near the bracing end connection. Studies have demonstrated the efficiency of the SHG connection in circular and square braces under monotonic tensile loading conditions, leading to the development of a design methodology based on the CSA S16 Steel Design Standard. However, limited research has been dedicated to investigating the compressive behaviour of this brace-connection configuration. A numerical parametric study was hence conducted to examine the inelastic response of the connection under reversed cyclic loading. Various parameters were considered, including the SHS size, the weld length and size, the brace slenderness, and the degree of confinement of the gusset plate. Designed based on the previously developed methodology, the simulated braces demonstrated their ability to withstand compressive loading cycles without fracturing at the connection, making it capacity design protected. The findings indicate that all confinement degrees of the gusset plate in the numerically tested models, from a constrained gusset plate to a linear clearance, led to the typical fracture initiation due to ultra-low-cycle fatigue away from the connection at the mid-length of the brace.

Keywords: Concentrically Braced Frames, steel braces, welded connections, seismic design

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background, objectives and methodology

Concentrically Braced Frames (CBFs) are a popular structural system used in seismic areas due to their inherent high stiffness. Hollow structural sections are often chosen as the bracing elements, which dissipate energy through inelastic cycles comprising yielding in tension and flexural buckling in compression. In accordance with capacity design principles, framing elements in the lateral load carrying path, e.g. beams, columns, foundations and brace connections, are designed to ensure that they possess sufficient capacity to withstand the expected forces exerted by the braces.

The so-called conventional connection between a hollow section brace, e.g. SHS, and a gusset plate is widely used; however, it has several serious drawbacks, including a reduced cross-section area, due to the slots in the tube, and unevenly distributed cross-section stresses, due to shear lag around the connection when subjected to tensile loading conditions. To avoid net section failure in the brace at the slot, reinforcement of the cross-section is typically required (1). The Slotted-Hidden-Gap (SHG) connection, as depicted in Fig. 1, has been developed to preclude the need for reinforcement of the

connection. It consists of a notched gusset plate inserted in the slotted brace member, where the welds start on the gross section of the tube. Once the connection has been manufactured, the space between the end of the notch in the gusset plate and the tube's slot end becomes hidden. The primary advantage of the SHG connection detail is to move the stress concentrations away from the net area of the tube.

Fig. 1. Slotted-Hidden-Gap (SHG) SHS brace connection and assembly of parts

Extensive research programs have been conducted on the SHG connection by Martinez-Saucedo et al. (2,3), Moreau (4) and Afifi (5) using circular (CHS) and square (SHS) bracing members to identify the key parameters influencing its behaviour when subjected to tensile loading. Due to the absence of specific recommendations in the Canadian Steel Design Standard CSA S16 (7) or other steel design standards, a design methodology was developed by Afifi et al. (6) for the SHG connection (Fig. 2). Despite Moreau (4) having conducted a reversed cyclic full-scale brace test as a proof of concept for the SHG connection, prior research has focused on the connection subjected to tensile loading, since it is often anticipated that the tensile resistance within the brace will be greater than the expected compressive strength. Furthermore, the connection's main challenge stems from the decreased tensile resistance, which arises due to the net section of the tube and shear lag. Therefore, the response of this connection when subjected to cyclic loading, with an emphasis on the compressive loading cycles, has not been specifically studied, making it the central focus of this research.

Fig. 2. Schematic drawing of the SHG connection with design variables

The objective of this research was to assess the Slotted-Hidden-Gap connection when subjected to a cyclic loading protocol to study its compressive behaviour. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was used for this purpose. To achieve this objective, the following steps were carried out: calibration study of a Finite Element Model (FEM) under reversed cyclic loading using the results of a full-scale SHG SHS brace tested by Moreau (4); and parametric FEA study under cyclic loading of the SHG connection elaborated from the design methodology developed by Afifi et al. (6).

2 CALIBRATION OF THE SLOTTED-HIDDEN-GAP FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

2.1 Laboratory-tested brace and connection

Moreau (4) carried out the cyclic testing of Specimen 12, a SHS 203×203×13 brace (Fig. 3a) with SHG connections (Fig. 3b,c) having an overlap ratio of L_{wg}/L_w (Fig. 2) of 15 %. The length of the SHS member was 4870 mm. A linear clearance of $2t_g$ was left between the brace's end and the line of constraint of the plate, to allow rotation of the gusset plate when the brace was flexed under compressive loading.

Fig. 3. Brace configuration of Specimen 12 : a) Schematic drawing of the SHG SHS Specimen 12, b) Photograph of the laboratory test by Moreau (4), c) close-up view of the bottom connection

The brace from Specimen 12 was fabricated with grade CSA G40.20-12 350W Class C (8) steel (nominal $F_y = 350$ MPa & $F_u = 450$ MPa; measured $F_y = 416$ MPa & $F_u = 472$ MPa). The gusset plates were fabricated from ASTM A572 Gr. 50 steel (9) (nominal $F_y = 345$ MPa & $F_u = 450$ MPa). The length and the size of the welds were chosen accordingly to avoid tensile and block-shear rupture of the brace, and to ensure adequate weld capacity. The global slenderness and width-to-thickness ratio of the SHS were compliant with the limits found in CSA S16 (7). An asymmetric tensile-dominant cyclic loading history was applied to the full brace. See Moreau (4) or Luu (1) for additional details on the laboratory test program.

2.2 Finite element model

The FEA model was built using Abaqus (10) to represent the laboratory-tested specimen, using the same geometry, material properties and boundary conditions as Specimen 12 (Moreau (4)). A full-brace model (Fig. 4) was generated to account for the residual stresses and buckling of the brace when subjected to a compressive force. To accurately replicate Specimen 12, AutoCad drawings were utilized to create the geometry of the full-brace, incorporating the measurements obtained from the tested specimen. The cold-forming manufacturing process is accounted for in the model by inputting an asymmetrical residual stress pattern to model the residual stress caused by the seam weld to close the cross-section. A longitudinal residual stress distribution from Suzuki & Lignos (11) was incorporated in the model using predefined fields in the initial step assuming one seam weld on one of the plain HSS walls. Peak values at the seam weld are taken as $1.0 F_y$ and decrease linearly to $-0.30 F_y$ in the corners of the brace. On the other hand, the transverse residual model is taken from

Koval (12), and varies through the thickness between $-0.6 \cdot F_y$ to $+0.6 F_y$ where the outer surface of the HSS is in tension and the inner surface in compression.

Fig. 4. Overall view of the FE mesh of Specimen 12

To account for the initial imperfections of the brace, a buckling analysis was performed beforehand where the first eigenmode was considered. The results of this analysis were integrated into the model by adjusting the nodal coordinates of the SHS through scaling the corresponding global buckling mode shape according to tolerances obtained in the manufacturing process of the steel members ($L/1000$). Due to the unrestricted rotation of the grips around the brace axis, all rotational degrees of freedom (DoFs) were allowed in the three directions for both ends. On the other hand, all translational DoFs were constrained on the strong floor structure side. The material plasticity was modelled with a combined hardening model with half cycle data type with two backstresses based on a refined version of the Voce-Chaboche constitutive model (13, 14) proposed by Hartloper et al. (15).

A solid 20-node brick quadratic mesh element C3D20R was utilized in the FEA model. The mesh size was established based on the calibration study conducted by Afifi (5), which involved performing a mesh sensitivity analysis. In order to accurately capture the characteristics of the weld region, a finer mesh was employed. A visual representation of the mesh applied to the full brace, with a closer look at the connection and gusset plate is provided in Fig. 4. Datum planes were employed to partition the components, ensuring a regular mesh that adheres to the geometry of the grips, as well as the slots in the SHS tube and gusset plates.

The equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) was utilized as a criterion for determining fracture initiation, i.e. in the critical area where the tested full-brace experienced local buckling at mid-length. A PEEQ value equal to unity at this location is indicative of a fracture initiation in the bracing member as reported by Zhao et al. (16). For other locations, typically at the corners of the SHS where different material properties are applied, a PEEQ value of 0.4 was assumed to define fracture initiation. A detailed description and assumptions used to develop the numerical model is found in the work of Luu (1).

2.3 Comparison of test and numerical prediction

The normalized force vs. displacement results obtained from Specimen 12 tested by Moreau (4) and the results from the FEA model are plotted in Fig. 5. The FEA model captures fairly accurately the ductility range and the yield limits, considering a global behaviour criterion where the force-displacement relationship is plotted. Both the model and test have IDRs varying between -1.8% to 2.9% prior to fracture initiation. The laboratory test exhibited a slightly stiffer behaviour, which could potentially be attributed to a different residual stress pattern compared to the one employed in the numerical model. A maximum difference of 27% between the post-buckling peaks can be explained by the theoretical as opposed to the measured account of the initial geometric imperfections employed in the FEA model. A comparison of the response history and the energy dissipation for the test and model was also carried out by Luu (1), further demonstrating the accuracy of the FEA model.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the normalized load-displacement response of Specimen 12 with the FEA model

3 STUDY OF HINGE ZONE OF GUSSET PLATE

3.1 Brace and connection configurations

To ensure that braces can yield in tension and buckle under compression when a building is subjected to a ground motion, it is crucial to detail properly their connection to the main frame to allow the member to act as a dissipative element. In cases of brace buckling, the gusset plate may experience out-of-plane bending due to end rotations of the brace. The allowance for plastic hinges in the gusset plate permits the post-buckled end rotation of the brace to be accommodated at relatively high storey drifts. As such, the developed finite element model was used in a parametric study to assess the behaviour of the gusset plate under cyclic loading, and to evaluate its impact on the performance of the SHG connection. Several parameters were varied, including; SHS size, weld configuration (short or long welds), brace slenderness, and clearance rule (linear, elliptical or constrained (Fig. 6)). A constant brace inclination was assumed, to ensure a consistent loading protocol for all numerical models. A total of twenty-one numerical models (Table 1) were generated and analysed using Abaqus, with a SHG connection present at both ends of each model.

In the parametric study, the SHS tubes were made of ASTM A1085 steel (17). The SHS sizes were chosen based on typical brace sizes that can be found in practice. Two different fillet weld configurations were implemented, where configuration B comprises equivalent longer length smaller-size welds compared to weld configuration A. A consistent overlap length ratio $L_{wg}/L_w = 15\%$ was used. Stockier bracing members tend to experience higher concentrations of plastic deformation at plastic hinges under compressive loading, leading to local buckling at critical locations. Therefore, it was chosen to adhere to CSA S16 to keep an overall slenderness limit under 100 in order to study the most critical cases.

In addition to the parameters incorporated in Afifi's design approach, the geometry of the clearance in the gusset plate was introduced as an additional parameter in the numerical study. Fig. 6 contains a visual representation of the three degrees of confinement of the gusset plate; a linear, elliptical and constrained hinge zone. The elliptical offset follows the equations provided by Lehman et al. (18) and the constrained configuration was determined arbitrarily, with the condition being to push the brace to its maximum extent toward the intersection of the beam and column, limiting the ability of the gusset to displace out-of-plane. Based on the work of Lehman et al., an elliptical gusset plate clearance model with an $8t_g$ offset distance was considered in this parametric study.

Table 1. Geometric properties of the brace and connection configurations

ID	SHS size	b_{cl}/t	L_{brace} [mm]	KL_H/r	Weld conf. D_w, L_w [mm]	Gusset plate t_g, W_g [mm]	Clearance
1AL1	SHS 127×127×6.4	15.1	4950	91.3	(A) 15, 200	13, 358	Linear $2t_g$
1AL2			5400	99.6			
1BL1			4950	91.3	(B) 10, 250	10, 416	
1BL2			5400	99.6			
2AL1	SHS 254×254×13	15.5	4950	45.5	(A) 30, 390	25, 705	Linear $2t_g$
2AL2			5400	49.6			
2BL1			4950	45.5	(B) 25, 475	18, 797	
2BL2			5400	49.6			
3AL1	SHS 305×305×16	15.8	4950	38.1	(A) 35, 440	33, 814	Linear $2t_g$
3AL2			5400	41.5			
3BL1			4950	38.1	(B) 30, 515	24, 900	
3BL2			5400	41.5			
1AC	SHS 127×127×6.4	15.1	4950	91.3	(A) 15, 200	13, 358	Constrained
1BC					(B) 10, 250	10, 416	Elliptical $8t_g$
1BE							
2AC	SHS 254×254×13	15.5	4950	45.5	(A) 30, 390	25, 705	Constrained
2BC					(B) 25, 475	18, 797	Elliptical $8t_g$
2BE							
3AC	SHS 305×305×16	15.8	4	38.1	(A) 35, 440	33, 814	Constrained
3BC					(B) 30, 515	24, 900	Elliptical $8t_g$
3BE							

Fig. 6. Degrees of confinement of the gusset plate for the SHS 254×254×13: a) 2AL1 (linear hinge zone), b) 2BE (elliptical hinge zone), c) 2AC (constrained hinge zone), d) 2BC (constrained hinge zone)

Fig. 7. Applied displacement history on the FEM (IDR vs. time)

Following the design methodology suggested by Afifi et al. (6), the net section fracture and block shear rupture have been verified for the SHS. Additionally, the block shear rupture has been verified for the gusset plate. Under compression, the design of the gusset plate takes into account the Whitmore section. Moreover, an additional verification has been included to ensure that the buckling of the gusset plate occurs after any potential fracture at the mid-length of the brace (see Luu (1)).

The developed FEA models incorporate identical boundary conditions, mesh types, and longitudinal and transverse residual stress patterns. The mesh size was adjusted according to the dimensions of the gusset plate and the length of the brace. Additionally, an elastic buckling analysis was conducted for each model to determine the shape of the initial geometric imperfections, and the obtained results of the node coordinates were scaled to respect a maximum lateral amplitude of $L_{brace}/1000$ and incorporated in the main analysis. A reversed cyclic loading protocol from Fell et al. (22) was used, where overall buckling of the brace is expected at a 0.2% drift (Fig. 7).

3.2 Results and discussion

The normalized load-displacement response of specimens 1AL1 to 3BL2, which exclusively feature a free hinge zone, are presented in Fig. 8. Each hysteretic curve is terminated when the PEEQ reaches a value of 1.0 at the mid-length of the brace. The braces were categorized by their length and weld configuration. All specimens exhibit a similar behaviour in tension for the first cycles, a visible reduction of the post-buckling loads and a decrease in the global axial stiffness of the bracing member.

While the width-to-thickness ratios are similar for all SHS sizes (15.1, 15.5, and 15.8, respectively from the smallest to the largest SHS), there is a variation in the overall slenderness ratio among these examples. Stockier braces exhibit lower ductility ranges due to their inherent higher stiffness which limits the ability to undergo significant plastic deformation. Conversely, they can achieve a higher compressive strength compared to slender braces. In tension, the three SHS sizes demonstrate a similar response in the first cycles. However, subsequent loading cycles are wider for stockier braces, indicating a greater capacity to dissipate energy for low displacements. Furthermore, analysing the force-displacement hysteretic curves, the buckling load is reached only once, whereas successive post-buckling loads during compressive cycles are significantly lower, which is the typical response of a single SHS brace. In contrast, during the tensile loading cycles, the yield limit is reached multiple times. This suggests that most of the plastic deformation occurs during the tensile cycles.

The buckled shape of the brace is influenced by the ability of the gusset plate to rotate. Fig. 9 offers a comparison among specimens 1AC, 1BC, 1BE and 1AL1. These are comprised of a constrained, elliptical $8t_g$ and linear $2t_g$ hinge zone configuration in the gusset plate, respectively. The corresponding hysteretic curves for the SHS 254×254×13 and SHS 305×305×16 are available in the thesis of Luu (1).

Fig. 8. Normalized load-displacement response of braces with a linear clearance zone in the gusset plate : a) weld conf. A, L = 4950 mm; b) weld conf. A, L = 5400 mm; c) weld conf. B, L = 4950 mm; d) weld conf. B, L = 5400 mm

Fig. 9. Normalized load-displacement response for SHS 127×127×6.4 with constrained, elliptical & linear hinge zone

The relationship between the equivalent plastic strain, measured on the SHS at the end of the welds and the drift is shown in Fig. 10. The graphs include both constrained and elliptical clearance in the gusset plate, considering both weld configurations. A star icon indicates a fracture initiation at the mid-length of the brace. To assess the influence on the PEEQ of the different degrees of confinement of the gusset plates, the graphs were extended to include configurations with a linear offset in the hinge zone. As anticipated, the connection configuration with an elliptical clearance exhibits lower

PEEQ values compared to a constrained configuration, with a maximum value reached at the potential fracture initiation of the brace's mid-length equal to 0.1 for specimen 3BE among all studied models. By incorporating either an elliptical or linear offset, a hinge zone was created, facilitating the rotation of the plate and consequently reducing the plastic deformation demands in the SHS at the front of the welds. On the other hand, a constrained configuration with a compact weld consistently resulted in the highest PEEQ values among the same SHS size.

Fig. 10. PEEQ vs. Drift measured on the SHS at the end of the welds with a constrained and elliptical hinge zone in the gusset plate : a) SHS 127×127×6.4; b) SHS 254×254×13

The von Mises stress distribution for the three gusset plate configurations (SHS 305×305×16) at the point of reaching their respective buckling load is shown in Fig. 11. The shorter-length larger-size weld (config. A) demonstrates a pronounced stress concentration on the gusset plate near the start of the slot in the SHS, whereas a longer-length smaller-sized weld (config. B) reveals a more uniform stress distribution at the ends of the tube. As anticipated, higher stresses are localized within the elliptical hinge zone in the gusset plate for the specimen 3BE, relieving the stresses at the ends of the brace.

Fig. 11. Von Mises stress distribution for the constrained and elliptical configuration for the SHS 305×305×16 at their respective buckling load

4 SUMMARY

The results of the load-displacement graphs demonstrate that slender braces (SHS 127×127×6.4) exhibit higher ductility ranges but a lower compressive strength compared to stockier braces (SHS 254×254×13 & SHS 365×365×16). The yield resistance is reached multiple times suggesting that the plastic strains accumulate during tensile loading cycles. Compressive loading cycles have a negligible impact on the equivalent plastic strains, which is a simplified metric to assess the corresponding fracture potential of the brace. Among all specimens, the constrained hinge zone combined with a short weld configuration exhibits the highest buckling resistance for SHS 127×127×6.4, SHS 254×254×13 & SHS 305×305×16 compared to the elliptical or linear configurations. Furthermore,

regarding the degree of confinement of the gusset plate, a linear hinge zone leads to lower axial forces and stiffness compared to an elliptical or confined hinge zone. Specimens with permitted hinge zones (linear and elliptical clearance) exhibit a different behaviour compared to the constrained configurations with lower moments, suggesting that a constrained hinge zone in the gusset plate forces the bending to occur in the SHS instead of the gusset plate. Moreover, von Mises stress distributions reveal that an elliptical hinge zone combined with a longer weld induces reduced stresses and a more uniform distribution along the length of the brace compared to other configurations, even at critical loads such as the buckling resistance or T_{max} . Near the slot end of the SHS, the PEEQ-drift analysis revealed that a potential fracture initiation at mid-length of the brace is likely, prior to failure at the slot end of the SHS for all brace sizes with a linear or elliptical gusset hinge configuration.

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